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**Universität
Basel**

NIP-HC: Process indicators for quality monitoring and quality development in home nursing care. A scoping review protocol

Study protocol – Version 1.0

Unibas

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1 Introduction

This review is part of a quality monitoring implementation and quality development project in the home nursing care setting in Switzerland.

1.1 Background of the overall project

Based on the quality strategy of the Swiss Federal Council, which aims to ensure and promote the quality of services in health care in Switzerland, the Federal Quality Commission (Eidgenössische Qualitätskommission, EQK) was established. (1) Among other things, the EQK advises the Federal Council on the definition of quality improvement measures in health care, commissions the development of new quality indicators (QIs) and the further development of existing QIs, and supports national and regional quality improvement projects. (2)

In contrast to other health care settings such as hospitals, quality development is less developed in the home care setting in Switzerland. Therefore, in 2025, the EKQ commissioned a project to establish QIs and implement a data-driven quality development program in the home care setting.

1.2 Overall project aim

The project aims at monitoring and developing quality of care in the provision of home nursing care by home care providers.

The aim of the overall project is:

- 1) to set up a national monitoring system for quality in home nursing care that can:
 - be used for monitoring quality in home nursing care providers and be a basis for quality contracts between home nursing care providers and the mandatory health insurers
 - serve as a basis for a benchmark between home care service providers and for quality development in home care service providers (via a cockpit function and based on a central data base)
 - be further developed in the future
- 2) to foster quality of care provision in home care providers in general (e.g. via the search and implementation of best practices for quality development in home care providers) as well as improving the quality of the collected data in home nursing care providers to improve the basis for the monitoring and the benchmark.

The project attempts to achieve these goals by searching and selecting valid and relevant QIs as a basis for quality monitoring and data-driven quality development and by searching, selecting and implementing quality development strategies in home care service organisations.

1.3 Background of the current scoping review

Work package 6 of NIP-HC examines quality indicators that are not part of the main interRAI-based outcome indicator work. Work package 6 includes a literature review on three topics: process quality indicators, patient-reported indicators, and indicators for interprofessional care. This protocol covers the review on process indicators only. Patient-reported indicators and interprofessional indicators will be treated in separate reviews. The findings of this review will support later NIP-HC steps. In particular, they will inform the Delphi work on process quality indicators, PROMs, PREMs, and interprofessional indicators. Therefore, they will inform whether process indicators could be included in the future quality development program and monitoring roadmap.

A quality indicator is a measurable item that can show a possible quality problem or a point for improvement. It can support monitoring, benchmarking, public reporting, internal feedback, or quality improvement. This review uses Donabedian's distinction between structure, process, and outcome indicators. (3) This review will focus on process indicators, which are defined as 'the actions and procedures that make up healthcare. Includes diagnoses, treatments, preventive care, and interpersonal interactions'. (3) Examples may include assessment, care planning, medication review, wound care, falls risk assessment, follow-up, documentation, referral, or client education.

1.4 Background of the current scoping review

Several reviews have already mapped quality indicators for home care or closely related community care settings. (4–11) These reviews show that process indicators are common, but they are often mixed with outcome, structure and patient experiences. Caughey et al. identified 226 indicators from public home care quality programs, including 68 process indicators; service delivery and care planning were among the most common domains. Joling et al. found that 455 of 567 community care indicators for older people measured care processes, mainly follow-up, monitoring, examinations, treatment, medication, and coordination. Other reviews and evidence reports add useful indicator domains, measurement details, and implementation issues, but they are either broader than home nursing care, focused on one country, or not focused mainly on process indicators. Therefore, this review will use these sources as seed references and will focus on extracting, describing, and judging the relevance of process indicators for professional home nursing care in the NIP-HC context.

2 Research objective

The objective of this scoping review is to identify and describe process indicators that are used, proposed, or tested to monitor and improve the quality of professional home care services for older people with medical or nursing care needs.

3 Theoretical framework and definitions

3.1 Definition of quality

We will apply two layers for defining and structuring quality:

- 1) the first layer will be Donabedian's framework for structuring Qis into structure, process or outcome. This review will solely focus on process indicators.
- 2) Furthermore, we will use the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the Federal Office of Public Health's (FOPH) definition of quality that encompasses the dimensions: safety, effectiveness, patient-centeredness, timeliness, efficiency, equitability and integratedness. (12)

3.2 Definition home (nursing) care

As the quality strategy of the Swiss Federal Council aims at improving health care covered by Swiss mandatory health insurance, the project will solely focus on developing the quality of home nursing care provision and exclude social support as well as other support services that are not covered by mandatory health insurance (13).

Based on this restriction we define home care as home nursing care, i.e. formal (paid) health care provided by home care service providers to clients living in the community (in their own home or in a living-with-services-facility) that receives nursing care services from a home care service provider. Social support services such as household help, meals on wheels, help with cooking or managing finances, social support or accompaniment, e.g. to doctor's appointments are excluded from the project. The same is true for other support systems or services e.g. falls alarm system, falls evaluation and adaptation of the home to prevent falls, dietician, health literacy sessions, etc.

4 PCC Framework

The following PCC Framework (Participants, Concept, context) is the basis for the review:

Participants: The main population is adults aged 65 years and older who live at home or in a living-with-services setting and receive home nursing care for medical or nursing care needs. Persons living in assisted living (with-services setting) and who receive care from a residential long-term care facility, and not from a home care providers, will be out of scope. Sources that include a broader adult home care population may be included if the process indicator can be relevant to older people or if results for older people or home nursing care can be separated.

Concept: The concept is process indicators for quality monitoring and quality development in home nursing care. A process indicator is defined as 'the actions and procedures that make up healthcare. Includes diagnoses, treatments, preventive care, and interpersonal interactions'. (3) The review will include indicators that are used in practice, used in public or internal quality monitoring, proposed in the literature, tested in a study, or included in a quality programme, manual, or indicator set.

Context: The context is professional home nursing care. This includes care delivered in the person's home by home care organisations, home health care services, Spitex-like services, or similar providers. Specialised home care areas, such as palliative home care, psychiatric home care, and children's home care will be excluded.

5 Methodology

The review will be conducted according to JBI guidance for scoping reviews. The review will also follow PRISMA-ScR reporting guidance in the final report. Several reviews have previously reported process quality indicators.

5.1 Databases and search strategy

The search will have two parts. First, the review team will use existing reviews and known indicator programmes as seed sources. (4–11) The indicator lists, supplements, references, and linked manuals of the existing reviews will be checked. This will help identify process indicators that were already covered by reviews before March 2025. Second, an update search will be done in electronic databases from March 2025 to the final search date. The start date is based on the most recent broad home care quality indicator review, which had its final search in March 2025. (11) Duplicates will be removed.

The planned databases are PubMed, Embase, CINAHL, and Scopus. Secondary strategies include screening reference lists and citation searching. Grey literature will also be searched. The grey literature search will focus on current indicator sets, quality programmes, and reporting manuals. Grey literature sources may include: national quality indicator libraries, government health authority websites, home care quality programmes, home care association websites, health system performance reporting websites, and reports from quality agencies.

The search string for Pubmed is reported in Appendix 1. This search string will be translated to the other databases. The search strategy for the grey literature is reported in Appendix 2.

5.2 Study selections

All citations will be imported into Endnote. Duplicates will be removed. A pilot screening will be done before full screening. The pilot will test if the inclusion criteria are clear. Titles and abstracts will be screened by one reviewer. Full texts of potentially relevant sources will be screened by two reviewers. Disagreements will be solved by discussion. A third reviewer will be involved if needed. Reasons for exclusion at full-text stage will be recorded. The source selection process will be shown in a PRISMA flow diagram.

5.3 Data extraction

Data extraction will be performed by a single reviewer using an Excel form, which will be pilot-tested on a selection of studies retained after full-text screening. The data extraction will capture the following

information: first author, doi, publication year, country, description of setting, study aim, study design, indicator definition, measurement details, target population, exclusion criteria, data source, risk adjustment, scale information where relevant, and reported use in quality monitoring or quality improvement.

5.4 Critical appraisal of quality of indicators

A formal critical appraisal of all included sources is not planned at this stage. The review will not exclude sources because of low study quality. However, the review will chart information that helps judge the possible usefulness of an indicator. This includes for example data on validity, reliability, feasibility, risk adjustment, and use in practice.

5.5 Data analysis and synthesis

The included studies will be presented in an overview table. All found QIs will be presented in a table, where QIs will be described according to the WHO quality dimensions.

5.6 Data management

The following information will be retained and archived on the institutional server: search string, Endnote file with study selection process, PDF of retrieved full text articles, data abstraction manual with variable definitions, Excel database with study data, Study report. The study report will be archived on Zenodo.

6 References

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2. Bundesamt für Gesundheit (BAG). 2026. 'Über Die EQK'. <https://www.bag.admin.ch/de/ueber-die-eqk>.
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5. Caughey GE, Rahja M, Harrison S, Fernando R, Inacio MC. Quality Indicators to Monitor Home Care Services for the Older Population: A Scoping Review. J Am Med Dir Assoc. 2025; 26(11):105876. doi:10.1016/j.jamda.2025.105876.
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11. Chen X, Ibrahim R, Lee YF, Hamid TA, Chai ST. Home-Based Community Elderly Care Quality Indicators in China: A Systematic Literature Review. Healthcare. 2025; 13(14):1637. doi:10.3390/healthcare13141637
12. World Health Organization. 2026. 'Quality of Care'. https://www.who.int/health-topics/quality-of-care#tab=tab_1.
13. Eidg. Dept des Innern (EDI),. 1996. Verordnung Des EDI Über Leistungen in Der Obligatorischen Krankenpflegeversicherung. Vol. 832.112.31.

7 Appendices

Appendix 1: Search string for pubmed

("Home Care Services"[Mesh] OR "Home Health Nursing"[Mesh] OR homecare[tiab] OR "home care"[tiab] OR "home-care"[tiab] OR "home healthcare"[tiab] OR "home health care"[tiab] OR "home health service*"[tiab] OR "home health nursing"[tiab] OR "home nursing"[tiab] OR "domiciliary care"[tiab] OR "domiciliary healthcare"[tiab] OR "domiciliary health care"[tiab] OR "in-home care"[tiab] OR "in home care"[tiab] OR "in-home aged care"[tiab] OR "in home aged care"[tiab] OR "home-based care"[tiab] OR "home based care"[tiab] OR "home-based aged care"[tiab] OR "home based aged care"[tiab] OR "home-based community care"[tiab] OR "home based community care"[tiab] OR "home and community-based service*"[tiab] OR "home- and community-based service*"[tiab] OR "home and community-based aged care"[tiab] OR "home- and community-based aged care"[tiab] OR HCBS[tiab] OR "long-term home care"[tiab] OR "home-based long-term care"[tiab] OR "visiting nurse*"[tiab] OR "visiting nursing"[tiab] OR Spitex[tiab])

AND

("Quality Indicators, Health Care"[Mesh] OR "Quality Assurance, Health Care"[Mesh] OR "Quality Improvement"[Mesh] OR "Outcome and Process Assessment, Health Care"[Mesh] OR "Process Assessment, Health Care"[Mesh] OR "Benchmarking"[Mesh] OR "quality indicator*"[tiab] OR "process indicator*"[tiab] OR "process quality indicator*"[tiab] OR "clinical indicator*"[tiab] OR "care indicator*"[tiab] OR "health care indicator*"[tiab] OR "healthcare indicator*"[tiab] OR "indicator set*"[tiab] OR "quality measure*"[tiab] OR "process measure*"[tiab] OR "process assessment"[tiab] OR "quality metric*"[tiab] OR "quality standard*"[tiab] OR "quality criterion"[tiab] OR "quality criteria"[tiab] OR "performance indicator*"[tiab] OR "performance measure*"[tiab] OR "quality assurance"[tiab] OR "quality assessment"[tiab] OR "quality monitoring"[tiab] OR "quality development"[tiab] OR "quality improvement"[tiab] OR "public reporting"[tiab] OR "quality reporting"[tiab] OR "quality framework*"[tiab] OR "quality domain*"[tiab] OR "quality monitoring system*"[tiab] OR "performance framework*"[tiab] OR "indicator framework*"[tiab] OR benchmark*[tiab] OR ((quality[tiab] OR performance[tiab] OR process[tiab]) AND (indicator*[tiab] OR measure*[tiab] OR metric*[tiab] OR standard*[tiab] OR criterion[tiab] OR criteria[tiab] OR benchmark*[tiab])))

Appendix 1: Search string for Embase

(

'home care'/exp

OR 'home nursing'/exp

OR 'home health agency'/exp

OR homecare:ti,ab,kw

OR 'home care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home-care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home healthcare':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home health care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home health service*':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home health nursing':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home nursing':ti,ab,kw

OR 'domiciliary care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'domiciliary healthcare':ti,ab,kw

OR 'domiciliary health care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'in-home care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'in home care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'in-home aged care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'in home aged care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home-based care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home based care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home-based aged care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home based aged care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home-based community care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home based community care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home and community-based service*':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home- and community-based service*':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home and community-based aged care':ti,ab,kw

OR 'home- and community-based aged care':ti,ab,kw

OR HCBS:ti,ab,kw

OR 'long-term home care':ti,ab,kw
OR 'home-based long-term care':ti,ab,kw
OR 'visiting nurse*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'visiting nursing':ti,ab,kw
OR Spitex:ti,ab,kw

)

AND

(

'clinical indicator'/exp
OR 'health care quality'/exp
OR 'quality improvement'/exp
OR 'quality assurance'/exp
OR 'quality control'/exp
OR 'quality control procedures'/exp
OR 'performance measurement system'/exp
OR 'outcome and process assessment (health care)'/exp
OR 'outcome assessment'/exp
OR 'benchmarking'/exp
OR 'quality indicator*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'process indicator*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'process quality indicator*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'clinical indicator*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'care indicator*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'health care indicator*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'healthcare indicator*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'indicator set*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality measure*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'process measure*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'process assessment':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality metric*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality standard*':ti,ab,kw

OR 'quality criterion':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality criteria':ti,ab,kw
OR 'performance indicator*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'performance measure*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality assurance':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality assessment':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality monitoring':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality development':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality improvement':ti,ab,kw
OR 'public reporting':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality reporting':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality framework*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality domain*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'quality monitoring system*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'performance framework*':ti,ab,kw
OR 'indicator framework*':ti,ab,kw
OR benchmark*:ti,ab,kw
OR (
 (quantity OR performance OR process) NEAR/3
 (indicator* OR measure* OR metric* OR standard* OR criterion OR criteria OR benchmark*)
):ti,ab,kw
)
AND [01-03-2025 to 26-06-2026]/pd

Scopus

(

TITLE-ABS-KEY(

homecare

OR "home care"

OR "home-care"

OR "home healthcare"

OR "home health care"

OR "home health service**"

OR "home health nursing"

OR "home nursing"

OR "domiciliary care"

OR "domiciliary healthcare"

OR "domiciliary health care"

OR "in-home care"

OR "in home care"

OR "in-home aged care"

OR "in home aged care"

OR "home-based care"

OR "home based care"

OR "home-based aged care"

OR "home based aged care"

OR "home-based community care"

OR "home based community care"

OR "home and community-based service**"

OR "home- and community-based service**"

OR "home and community-based aged care"

OR "home- and community-based aged care"

OR HCBS

OR "long-term home care"

OR "home-based long-term care"

OR "visiting nurse*"

OR "visiting nursing"

OR Spitex

)

)

AND

(

TITLE-ABS-KEY(

"quality indicator*"

OR "process indicator*"

OR "process quality indicator*"

OR "clinical indicator*"

OR "care indicator*"

OR "health care indicator*"

OR "healthcare indicator*"

OR "indicator set*"

OR "quality measure*"

OR "process measure*"

OR "process assessment"

OR "quality metric*"

OR "quality standard*"

OR "quality criterion"

OR "quality criteria"

OR "performance indicator*"

OR "performance measure*"

OR "quality assurance"

OR "quality assessment"

OR "quality monitoring"

OR "quality development"

OR "quality improvement"

OR "public reporting"

OR "quality reporting"

OR "quality framework*"

OR "quality domain*"

OR "quality monitoring system*"

OR "performance framework*"

OR "indicator framework*"

OR benchmark*

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OR

TITLE-ABS-KEY(

(quality OR performance OR process)

W/3

(indicator* OR measure* OR metric* OR standard* OR criterion OR criteria OR benchmark*)

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Cinahl

(

(MH "Home Health Care+")

OR (MH "Home Nursing")

OR (MH "Home Nursing, Professional")

OR TI (homecare OR "home care" OR "home-care" OR "home healthcare" OR "home health care" OR "home health service*" OR "home health nursing" OR "home nursing" OR "domiciliary care" OR "domiciliary healthcare" OR "domiciliary health care" OR "in-home care" OR "in home care" OR "in-home aged care" OR "in home aged care" OR "home-based care" OR "home based care" OR "home-based aged care" OR "home based aged care" OR "home-based community care" OR "home based community care" OR "home and community-based service*" OR "home- and community-based service*" OR "home and community-based aged care" OR "home- and community-based aged care" OR HCBS OR "long-term home care" OR "home-based long-term care" OR "visiting nurse*" OR "visiting nursing" OR Spitex)

OR AB (homecare OR "home care" OR "home-care" OR "home healthcare" OR "home health care" OR "home health service*" OR "home health nursing" OR "home nursing" OR "domiciliary care" OR "domiciliary healthcare" OR "domiciliary health care" OR "in-home care" OR "in home care" OR "in-home aged care" OR "in home aged care" OR "home-based care" OR "home based care" OR "home-based aged care" OR "home based aged care" OR "home-based community care" OR "home based community care" OR "home and community-based service*" OR "home- and community-based service*" OR "home and community-based aged care" OR "home- and community-based aged care" OR HCBS OR "long-term home care" OR "home-based long-term care" OR "visiting nurse*" OR "visiting nursing" OR Spitex)

OR SU (homecare OR "home care" OR "home-care" OR "home healthcare" OR "home health care" OR "home health service*" OR "home health nursing" OR "home nursing" OR "domiciliary care" OR "domiciliary healthcare" OR "domiciliary health care" OR "in-home care" OR "in home care" OR "in-home aged care" OR "in home aged care" OR "home-based care" OR "home based care" OR "home-based aged care" OR "home based aged care" OR "home-based community care" OR "home based community care" OR "home and community-based service*" OR "home- and community-based service*" OR "home and community-based aged care" OR "home- and community-based aged care" OR HCBS OR "long-term home care" OR "home-based long-term care" OR "visiting nurse*" OR "visiting nursing" OR Spitex)

)

AND

(

(MH "Quality Indicators, Health Care")

OR (MH "Clinical Indicators")

OR (MH "Quality of Health Care+")

OR (MH "Quality Assurance+")

OR (MH "Quality Improvement")

OR (MH "Outcome and Process Assessment (Health Care)+")

OR (MH "Process Assessment (Health Care)+")

OR (MH "Outcome Assessment+")

OR (MH "Benchmarking")

OR TI ("quality indicator*" OR "process indicator*" OR "process quality indicator*" OR "clinical indicator*" OR "care indicator*" OR "health care indicator*" OR "healthcare indicator*" OR "indicator set*" OR "quality measure*" OR "process measure*" OR "process assessment" OR "quality metric*" OR "quality standard*" OR "quality criterion" OR "quality criteria" OR "performance indicator*" OR "performance measure*" OR "quality assurance" OR "quality assessment" OR "quality monitoring" OR "quality development" OR "quality improvement" OR "public reporting" OR "quality reporting" OR "quality framework*" OR "quality domain*" OR "quality monitoring system*" OR "performance framework*" OR "indicator framework*" OR benchmark*)

OR AB ("quality indicator*" OR "process indicator*" OR "process quality indicator*" OR "clinical indicator*" OR "care indicator*" OR "health care indicator*" OR "healthcare indicator*" OR "indicator set*" OR "quality measure*" OR "process measure*" OR "process assessment" OR "quality metric*" OR "quality standard*" OR "quality criterion" OR "quality criteria" OR "performance indicator*" OR "performance measure*" OR "quality assurance" OR "quality assessment" OR "quality monitoring" OR "quality development" OR "quality improvement" OR "public reporting" OR "quality reporting" OR "quality framework*" OR "quality domain*" OR "quality monitoring system*" OR "performance framework*" OR "indicator framework*" OR benchmark*)

OR SU ("quality indicator*" OR "process indicator*" OR "process quality indicator*" OR "clinical indicator*" OR "care indicator*" OR "health care indicator*" OR "healthcare indicator*" OR "indicator set*" OR "quality measure*" OR "process measure*" OR "process assessment" OR "quality metric*" OR "quality standard*" OR "quality criterion" OR "quality criteria" OR "performance indicator*" OR "performance measure*" OR "quality assurance" OR "quality assessment" OR "quality monitoring" OR "quality development" OR "quality improvement" OR "public reporting" OR "quality reporting" OR "quality framework*" OR "quality domain*" OR "quality monitoring system*" OR "performance framework*" OR "indicator framework*" OR benchmark*)

OR TI ((quality OR performance OR process) N3 (indicator* OR measure* OR metric* OR standard* OR criterion OR criteria OR benchmark*))

OR AB ((quality OR performance OR process) N3 (indicator* OR measure* OR metric* OR standard* OR criterion OR criteria OR benchmark*))

OR SU ((quality OR performance OR process) N3 (indicator* OR measure* OR metric* OR standard* OR criterion OR criteria OR benchmark*))

)

AND DT 20250301-20260626

Appendix 2: Grey literature searches:

1. "home care" "quality report"
2. "home care" "quality" "public reporting"
3. "home care" "quality indicator*"
4. "home care" "quality measure*"
5. "home care" "performance"
6. "home care" "quality development"
7. "home care" "quality improvement"

Note, searches will be restricted to first 50 hits in Google